

According to Begon et al.¹, the takahe (*Porphyrio hochstetteri*) is a large, herbivorous, flightless bird thought to be extinct until it was rediscovered in 1948 living in the remote Murchison Mountains on the South Island of New Zealand.

Takahe (*Porphyrio hochstetteri*)

Source: Government of New Zealand, Department of Conservation (2013).

Interestingly, based on the locations of fossil remains of *Porphyrio hochstetteri*, the species was once wide spread on the South Island in its fundamental niche, mainly at altitudes below 300 meters in forests, scrublands, and grasslands (with tussocks of the genus *Chionochloa*, a preferred food source)². However, ecologic pressures from food competition from the red deer (*Cervus elaphus scoticus*), predation by stoats (*Mustella erminea*) and humans, eventually resulted in the takahe occupying a narrow realized niche of alpine pasture.

Murchison Mountains, South Island, New Zealand

Source: Government of New Zealand, Department of Conservation (2014).

Using the historical fundamental niche reconstructed from fossil evidence, a conservation program for *Porphyrio hochstetteri* was designed by the government of New Zealand, Department of Conservation. Members of the species were translocated to islands away from competition and predators. While the conservation program has demonstrated some success facilitating a self-sustaining *Porphyrio hochstetteri* population, the islands did not provide an optimal habitat, specifically, "... island birds have poorer hatching and fledging success than mountain birds."³ Apparently the island environment did not provide an optimal match to *Porphyrio hochstetteri* historical fundamental niche.

Takahē (*Porphyrio hochstetteri*)

Source: Government of New Zealand, Department of Conservation (2013).

¹ Begon, M. et al., 2006. Ecology: from Individuals to Ecosystems. Oxford: Blackwell

² Trewick, S.A, Worthy, T. H., 2001. Origins and Prehistoric Ecology of Takahē based on Morphometric, Molecular, and Fossil Data, in Begon, M. et al., 2006. Ecology: from Individuals to Ecosystems. Dunedin: University of Otago Press

³ Jamison, I.G., Ryan, C.J., 2001. Island Takahē: Closure of the Debate over the Merits of Introducing Fiordland to predator-free islands, in Begon, M., et al., 2006. Ecology: from Individuals to Ecosystems. Dunedin: University of Otago Press